
Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic **FLEXi**bility
services in the distribution **GRID**

Project Website
Deliverable 9.4
WP9

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DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

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Dissemination level	
X	PU → Public
	PP → Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC)
	RE → Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC)
	CO → Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Approvals

	Company
Author/s	CIRCE
Task Leader	CIRCE
WP Leader	CIRCE

Documents History

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2	10/01/2020	1 st Version	CIRCE
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ABBREVIATIONS

PC: Project Coordinator
CA: Consortium Agreement
CC: Communication Committee
DoA: Description of Action
EC: European Commission
GA: General Assembly
IPR: Intellectual Property Right
KPI: Key Performance Indicator
M: Month
PH: Project Handbook
R&D: Research and Development
SC: Steering Committee
TP: Technical Partner
WP: Work Package
SME: Small and Medium Enterprise
DMP: Data Management Plan
H2020: Horizon 2020

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The FLEXIGRID website (which can be accessed through the URL <http://www.flexigrid-h2020.eu/>) was completed and made operational at the end of January 2020 (M4). It contains all institutional information about the project and is intended to be used as the entry point to the FLEXIGRID project for both the public and scientific / professional communities and other stakeholders' categories, including end-users. Besides that, the website acts as communication and dissemination channel for the project's results and for the involvement of the stakeholders.

The FLEXIGRID website is the central dissemination channel of the project and it will ensure the largest possible impact and dissemination. It is part of the bigger communication strategy that is carried out in the framework of WP9 under CIRCE's guidance.

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1 INTRODUCTION

The Project Website is developed in the WP9 of Communication and Dissemination and its included in Task 9.2 as tool for the dissemination of the project.

This deliverable contains the main feature of the website of the FLEXIGRID project and aims at disseminating the project details and results to a wider audience (not only industry and scientific communities, but also media, national and European policy makers, relevant stakeholders and general public). The website will provide information about the project including aims and objectives, technological implications, partner lists, funding details, links to related sites and information on exploitable results for industry and investors. It will also promote upcoming project events and offer links to related projects and social media.

2 FLEXIGRID WEBSITE

The website has been designed by CIRCE following the needs of the project and the Description of Action. The key aspects can be summarised in the following points.

- **Website domain:** The domain name (<http://www.flexigrid-h2020.eu/>) was registered in the month of December 2019.
- **Website scope:** Coherently with the FLEXIGRID Description of Work, the website functions as a first access to general information about the project. Therefore, it features in the homepage links to internal pages containing information about the project and the sites where it is demonstrated.
- **Website layout and identity:** The visual identity has not been fully developed but will follow be based on the actual project identity shown at the website. The website is structured to be easy to browse. The colours and font were chosen according to the guidelines that will be included in the project identity set.

2.1 Website Structure

The website provides information about the project including aims and objectives, partner lists, pilot and follower locations, dissemination materials, news and links to related sites and information on exploitable results for industry and investors. The homepage will communicate the main aspects of the project also will promote upcoming project events and offer links to related projects.

Interoperable solutions for implementing holistic FLEXibility services in the distribution GRID

Figure 1. FLEXIGRID Homepage

Much relevance is given to the Demo Sites, that are the main point of the project. The Homepage contains direct links to this section (Figure 2)

Figure 2. FLEXIGRID Homepage dedicated to Demo Sites

Besides, the footer of the website which appears in all pages, homepage or content page and contains link to website sections, legal and cookies policy regulation, contact information, the social media and the EU funding acknowledgement with the emblem (Figure 3).

Figure 3. FLEXIGRID Homepage footer content

The implementation of the contents of the FLEXIGRID website has taken place since Month 4 and will continue throughout the duration of the project life. The website is structured in a homepage and five main sections. These sections are listed in the following bullet points:

2.1.1 The Project

Contains an overall description of the project, aimed at users looking for a deeper level of technical and practical information. It highlights three sub-sections describing the concept of the project, the objectives and solutions to be developed during FLEXIGRID project.

- **About the project** sub-section; details the innovative concept of FLEXIGRID project and how it fits into the context of the European clean energy transition. Its highlights the ambition of the project, its key role in the improvement of the distribution grids, the solutions to be developed and a brief explanation of the partners representing all the energy value chain.
- The sub-section **Objectives**; aims to present concretely the FLEXIGRID. The project objectives are presented as a puzzle of 8 goals. Each piece is interactive and explain in detail the objective (Figure 4).
- **Solutions** sub-sections; shows 8 innovative solutions to be developed to making more flexible, reliable and costs-efficient the main objective of FLEXIGRID project. Furthermore, it considering as another solution the single open source platform “Fuse” which main role will be integrate the different solutions making them interoperable with the IT systems used by the energy stakeholders, increasing its replication potential.

Figure 4. FLEXIGRID The project objectives

2.1.2 Partners

This section shows the consortium partners involved in the project and their role. Fifteen interactive boxes show each partner's logo and allow to click on it to reveal information about the organisation, the main responsibilities within the project and a direct link to their websites. In addition, this section presents the consortium members classified in three groups with different roles: 1) **Technology developers**, which will focus on the development of the FLEXIGRID hardware and software solutions as well as the ICT framework; 2) **Demo-sites** which will provide data, support and test the developed solutions. 3) **Transversal partners**, which will provide a horizontal support to the rest of the consortium by means of carrying out exploitation and dissemination activities (Figure 5).

TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPERS

 FUNDACIÓN CIRCE SEE MORE	 VERD SEE MORE	 UNIVERSITY OF ZAGREB SEE MORE	 UNIVERSITY OF CANTABRIA SEE MORE	 LINKS SEE MORE
 ORMAZABAL SEE MORE	 ZIV SEE MORE	 HYPERTECH SEE MORE	 ATOS SEE MORE	 SELTA SEE MORE

DEMO-SITES

 VIESGO SEE MORE	 MAKRYAMMOS SEE MORE	 HEP-ODS SEE MORE	 EDYNA SEE MORE
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TRANSVERSAL

CAPENERGIES
[SEE MORE](#)

Figure 5. FLEXIGRID Consortium members

2.1.3 Demos

This is the main section of the webpage in which 4 Demos sites and different use cases, are presented as a cornerstone of the project, to carry out the demonstration campaign and foster the replicability.

- **Use Cases** sub-section describes 8 different use cases previously identified addressing most common EU distribution grid problems. These use cases are presented in 8 interactive boxes allowing to show detailed information in one click.

- Each **Demo** has its own sub-section (*Demo I, II, III & IV*) with useful information as location and general description, the main challenges and the innovation and solutions expected to achieve during the project lifetime. Figure 6, shows the Spanish Demo site.

Figure 6. FLEXI:GRID Spanish Demo site

2.1.4 Publications

This section will contain all the public dissemination material and documents in order to allow any interested audience to obtain a deeper content and detail of FLEXI:GRID project. This section lists all the public deliverables and publications issued by the project available for consultation or download. It may contain videos, flyers, info-packs, scientific papers and other public deliverables. This section will be regularly updated as more public content will be generated.

The following sub-sections have been created to distribute all dissemination:

- **Deliverables** sub-sections will allow to every person the download all the public materials that will be developed and will be uploaded on the website once approved by the European Commission.
- **Dissemination material** sub-section will offer all the dissemination material available for download such as a project poster, logos, the main project presentation. This sub-section will be uploaded continuously.

Overview of the project – FLEXI:GRID

FLEXI:GRID POSTER

Figure 7. FLEXI:GRID website Publications section

2.1.5 News

One of the dynamic parts of the website with regularly updated press and news releases around the project topics. This section lists all the news about the project, sorted by most recent, that will be stored in order to be available at the general public. In the main page users can read a short excerpt of the news and then go deeper on each news item's page. News will be stored and showed in chronological order.

This section will be regularly updated with the most interesting fairs, conferences and workshops relevant for the sector and organized or promoted by the project. In the main page users can read a short excerpt of the event's description and then go deeper on each event's page.

Figure 8. FLEXI:GRID website News section

2.2 Additional information

2.2.1 Legal Disclaimer and Privacy Policy

The Privacy and Cookie Policy of the FLEXIGRID is accessible via a link included in the website footer. It ensures that personal data of users is processed according to the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation). All website visitors implicitly accept these terms of utilisation.

FLEXIGRID The project Partners Demos Publications News Home / Legal

1.- Website Holder
 Corporate Name: Fundación CIRCE
 ID Number: G-50556091
 Registered Domicile: Parque Empresarial Dinamiza, Avenida Ranillas, 3D
 City: Zaragoza -50018-
 Country: Spain
 Email Address: protecciondatos@fcirce.es
 Telephone: 0034976976859
 Corporate website: www.flexigrd-h2020.eu

2.- Person responsible for processing

Pursuant to the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, the Fundación Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos, with Fiscal I.D. Code (C.I.F.) G-50556091, with registered offices at Parque Empresarial Dinamiza, Avenida Ranillas 3D (Zaragoza), and telephone 976976859 (hereinafter, "CIRCE" or the "Foundation") informs its users of www.fcirce.es (the "Website") of the conditions in the processing of their personal information through this Privacy and Cookie Policy.

3.- Purposes and legal basis for processing

CIRCE collects personal information from the users through different forms and e-mails contained in the Website:

Categories	Main data collected	Purpose and Legal Basis
	First and Last Names, Identification (DNI, NIE or Passport), Telephone, e-mail and password for creation of user.	
	Company or organization.	

Figure 9. FLEXIGRID Privacy Policy Disclaimer

The FLEXIGRID website is responsive. Its layout and contents adapt to the size of different screens thus providing an easy surfing by mobile devices. The website is accessible via smartphones at the same address.

The website structure and its associated databases (registered users) are administered by CIRCE, which manages the overall content updates with contributions by the other consortium partners.

2.2.2 Updates

The FLEXIGRID project website will be updated regularly to reflect the current state of its progress and will continue to be updated for the entire duration of the project as well as after its completion.

Additionally, the updating of the social media profiles will take place regularly by the authorised members of the CIRCE team and other involved beneficiaries and keep the followers/friends/connections up to date regarding the FLEXIGRID innovations and findings.

The texts for the FLEXIGRID website were drafted in a journalistic, easy-to-read style so that non-experts can also understand what the project is about. Illustrations, explanatory figure and pictures, as well as short texts with bullet points and emphasised text parts were favoured over long descriptions.

Moreover, the website will regularly provide new downloadable content which will be available on the website, such as communication materials and the public project deliverables.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The current status of the FLEXIGRID website fully matches the objectives of Task 9.2 of WP9. Contents, which represent a core part of it, will be added in parallel with the progress of the projects' activities and regularly updated until the end of the project.

With all these measures, including a graphically appealing, easy text formats and well-structured contents, CIRCE and the other Consortium partners have laid the ground for an impactful website that attracts many visitors and will be the main communication channel for the project duration.

The website is effectively connected to all the other social media accounts of the project to guarantee an interactive and fruitful project communication.

CIRCE will regularly update the content in the sections and sub-sections of the website, upload relevant material and publish news items as well as related events and project events. Only by keeping the website up to date, it is possible to ensure a maximum outreach potential for the project communication and dissemination. In the coming months, it will be crucial to fill the website with even more content and details.

CIRCE has set up monitoring tools to continuously control the website traffic and evaluate the success of the project website also to report its effectiveness to EC and the whole project Consortium.

DISSEMINATION POTENTIAL (NOT TO BE SUBMITTED TO THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION)

To be filled by the DLV responsible

What's the confidentiality degree of this deliverable?		<input type="checkbox"/> Total	<input type="checkbox"/> Partly	<input type="checkbox"/> Public
Being "Partly" the confidentiality, what are the results that might be disseminated?				
1				
2				
3				
Main stakeholders to be addressed by the results of the deliverable				
Name	Type	Sector	Contribution to the project	
1				
2				
3				
Main events related to the results of the deliverable				
Title	Date	Press release	Target audience	
1				
2				
3				
Dissemination tools: what sort of materials can be created to contribute to disseminate the results?				
<input type="checkbox"/> Photographs	<input type="checkbox"/> Video	<input type="checkbox"/> Power point	<input type="checkbox"/> Papers	<input type="checkbox"/> Poster
<input type="checkbox"/> News for project website	<input type="checkbox"/> Networking opportunities	<input type="checkbox"/> Training course	<input type="checkbox"/> Seminar	<input type="checkbox"/> Social network
Potential Paper				
Title	Authors			
Abstract / Public summary (500 words)				

Other dissemination suggestion or comments from the DLV authors

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